

Strategy of the Riau Provincial Government and Responsible Stakeholders in Handling Covid-19 in Riau Province

Dimas Raka Kurniawan Putra¹, Syamsul Ma'arif², Lilik Kurniawan³, Adela Oktavia Islami⁴, Alif Hanugrah Insan Nanda Pratama⁵

¹ (Student in Disaster Management Department, Republic of Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

² (Professor in Disaster Management Department, Republic of Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

³ (Chief Secretary, National Disaster Management Authority, Indonesia)

⁴ (Student in Disaster Management Department, Republic of Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

⁵ (Student in Disaster Management Department, Republic of Indonesia Defense University, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT: The Covid-19 problem in Riau Province must be anticipated together because on February 9, 2022 it continues to increase. Covid-19 continues to increase, especially in Riau Province. In the case of rising Covid-19 cases, the government must be prepared to deal with these conditions. Not only the government, all stakeholders engaged in this field must also participate in handling Covid-19 in Riau. This research focuses on the strategy of the Riau provincial government and stakeholders who are responsible for handling Covid-19 in Riau Province. The research methodology used is qualitative research with data collection techniques through interviews and Focused Group Discussion (FGD). The results of this study are that the Covid-19 disaster management in Riau Province is classified as very good. It can be seen from the Riau Government's preparedness indicators which prepare regulations and the implementation of disaster risk reduction for the spread of Covid-19 and the effectiveness of these regulations. Every stakeholder also helps in handling Covid-19 such as several companies that carry out CSR in the form of distributing hand sanitizers, masks and other necessities. The Riau Regional Police also participated in the Covid-19 disaster management, namely by distributing vaccines in disadvantaged, frontier, outermost places so that the spread of vaccines ran smoothly.

KEYWORDS - Covid-19; Government; Riau Province; Stakeholder

I. INTRODUCTION

The spread of Covid-19 in Indonesia, the Government officially announced the first Covid-19 case in Indonesia on March 2, 2020. Two positive Indonesian citizens said that they had direct contact with Japanese citizens who were visiting Indonesia. On March 11, 2020, for the first time there was a case of death caused by the corona virus. The victim who died was a 59-year-old man from Solo. It was discovered he had contracted the infection after attending a seminar in Bogor in February. The problem of Covid-19, especially in Riau Province, must be anticipated together. And at this time, the spread of Covid-19 cases in Riau Province as of February 9, 2022 experienced a significant increase compared to the number of cases at the beginning of January 2022. This spike in cases is in line with the trend that has occurred throughout Indonesia since the first case of transmission of the Omicron variant of Covid-19 detected in Jakarta. The trend of daily cases of Covid-19 in Riau Province can be seen on Fig 1

Figure 1. Graph of Covid-19 in Riau Province January 1, 2022 to February 8, 2022

(<https://corona.riau.go.id/>)

According to data quoted from corona.riau.go.id on February 10, 2022, Riau Province has a total of 129,877 confirmed cases of Covid-19 with Pekanbaru City having the highest case of 52,885 cases and followed by Dumai City with 10,365 cases. Initially, the evolution of this new virus and disease was unknown before the outbreak in Wuhan, China at the end of 2019. Currently, Covid-19 has become a pandemic that attacks almost all countries in any hemisphere (World Health Organization, 2020).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Symptoms of Covid-19

In the characteristics, Covid-19 can cause mild to severe pneumonia, as well as very fast transmission and can occur between humans. Covid-19 is very sensitive to ultraviolet light (UV light) and heat and can be inactivated effectively with almost any disinfectant. However, the use of hand sanitizers containing chlorhexidine is not recommended (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2020). Clinically, Covid-19 has its own symptoms and characters, such as the incubation period of Covid-19 ranging from 1 to 14 days and generally occurring from 3 to 7 days (Safrizal, et al, 2020). Other studies also say that the signs and symptoms experienced by someone who has been infected with the Covid-19 virus will appear on days 2 to 14 after being exposed to the virus (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2020). Symptoms experienced by people with Covid-19 include: a. Fever; b. Cough; c. shortness of breath or difficulty breathing; d. Tired and easily tired; e. Pain in the muscles or the whole body; f. Headache; g. Loss of the ability to taste and smell; h. Sore throat; i. Nasal congestion.

2.2 Pentahelix

Etymologically pentahelix comes from penta which means five and helix is a braid. The Pentahelix approach is based on five kinds of stakeholders, namely academia, business, community, government and media. This approach aims to help manage the complexity of a role or actor-based problem or problem. One form of multiculturalism in disaster management, especially disasters that occurred in Indonesia is the concept of pentahelix cooperation. The composition of the diversity of entities can be managed based on a collaborative governance approach. Collaborative governance is a government arrangement in which public institutions directly engage non-state stakeholders in deliberative joint decision-making processes. This collaboration aims to address problems in the community through a series of factors that are very important in the collaborative process. Disaster management efforts are not only the responsibility of the government, but also all relevant stakeholders. For this reason, a collaborative approach is key in dealing with the Covid-19 disaster, starting from curative action, promotive action and preventive action.

As research conducted by Rahmawati, et al (2021) who examined resilient villages: a form of collaboration between stakeholders in responding to the Covid-19 pandemic which resulted in the success of the Tangguh Semeru village program involving the entire community in breaking the chain of Covid-19 spread. . Because with the Tangguh Village program, the officers who provide socialization to the community can run better. The community also participates in creating public awareness of suppressing the spread of Covid-19 (Rahmawati, et al., 2020). There is also a study conducted by Widyati and Widana (2020) which found that the

community and the apparatus played a role in the spread of Covid-19. The capacity of health services in dealing with Covid-19 has improved. There is independence in the manufacture of drugs and vaccines to reduce the impact of Covid-19 (Widyati and Widana, 2020)

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Methodology The research conducted by the researcher in this study is a qualitative research methodology which means that the method used to explore and understand a social or humanitarian problem of an individual or group (Creswell, 1998). The research design used by the researcher is descriptive qualitative, namely through data collection and analysis in qualitative methods supported by information obtained during the research and literature review using secondary data. Then the information that has been obtained is processed into a study in the discussion of this research.

The time of the research was carried out from February 8, 2022 to February 10, 2022. The research location was in Riau Province which was carried out online during the 2022 Defense University Domestic Work Lecture which was attended by the Riau Regional Police Kabbidokes, Indragiri Hilir Regency BPBD, and the Provincial Health Office Riau.

Data collection techniques used were through Focus Group Discussions (FGD), interviews and using secondary data, starting with data obtained from relevant stakeholder websites, regional regulations and other documents that could support this research.

IV. CONCLUSION

The Disaster Management Cycle is divided into four cycles, namely prevention and mitigation, preparedness, emergency response and recovery. As can be seen in figure 2.

Figure 2. Disaster Management Cycle
Source : Triutomo, et.al., (2011)

Figure 2 shows that there are quadrants which are several stages in disaster management which does not mean that the stages are carried out sequentially. As a cycle, each stage of disaster management is carried out with different activities, including: 1. Prevention and mitigation, which is carried out in a situation where there is no disaster, which aims to minimize the impact of the disaster; 2. Preparedness, which is carried out when there is a potential disaster that might occur so that you know how to respond and deal with the disaster; 3. Emergency response carried out in the event of a disaster with the aim of reducing the increasing number of victims; 4. Recovery is carried out during safe post-disaster conditions and aims to restore community activities back.

During the prevention and mitigation period, the Riau Provincial government, especially the Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) Indragirihilir carried out prevention and mitigation in the form of preventive actions such as going directly to the field for spraying disinfectants using standard equipment, traversing remote areas and areas where there were a lot of crowds, And after positive cases rose quite quickly,

all officers involved had started to move with regional restrictions, patrols, guarding in border areas, with an invitation to wear masks (BPBD Indragirihilir, 2022).

As the Acting Head of the Riau Provincial Health Office said that prevention is better than cure, therefore the budget made for prevention is much larger for health services such as pamphlets, discussions of various media, to provide awareness to the public regarding the adverse effects of high positive numbers. from covid. In addition to pamphlets in shopping centers, shops, billboards, about the dangers of omicron, there is also socialization on provincial television and has become a paradigm that this disease is dangerous (Plt Head of the Health Service, 2022).

The Head of the Health Doctors Division (Kabbidokes) of the Riau Police also plays a role in preventing and mitigating in Riau Province in terms of law enforcement regarding actions that violate the law during the Covid-19 pandemic. The Riau Police Kabbidokes also said that the Riau Regional Police's commitment in this matter was to accelerate vaccination only, some colleagues at the puskesmas who were not supportive of the distribution of our vaccines also took very firm action regarding this, for example in his non-position, one of the heads of the puskesmas obstructed the distribution of vaccines. (Kabbidokes Riau Police, 2022).

During the preparedness period, the BPBD of Indragiri Hilir Regency used direct education and then conducted education through online media because people rarely open online media, even in remote areas, many people do not understand what is conveyed in the print media. The Head of Dokkes of the Riau Police also said that there were no difficult things for Brimob. The assistance mentioned earlier is a form of the seriousness of the Kapolda in this vaccination activity, including leading each stakeholder in Riau Province himself. In Riau province no coercion was ever given because the refusal was so strong that we had to impose coercion on one region/group. However, some misconceptions can arise from fake news or public ignorance of vaccines. We also convey that the problem in Riau is more with parents' concerns about vaccinating their children (Kabbidokes Polda Riau, 2022).

The Acting Head of the Health Office said that for the contingency plan the Health Office coordinated every month, we keep the BOR available, with predictions to anticipate this increase in patients, and of course adjustments in hospital services, including hospital reserves, including the sports building as a backup in case of an explosion in the number of covid (Plt Head of the Health Service, 2022).

During the emergency response period, the Riau Provincial Government focused on hospital based which was supported by the regional government and the provincial government. For the lab itself, the Riau Provincial Government uses facilities from the hospital. Then at this time the BPBD of Indragiri Hilir Regency gave an example from himself and among them began educating this matter to every RT/RW related to cleanliness and disinfection by holding meetings and collecting data on residents. Although tribal people lack education, in terms of participation, they are actually easier to invite and foster. When we carried out socialization activities and vaccines, the average community actually took part and did not show any resistance at all. The task force is a form of the government's quick reaction to the downstream Indragiri. Here we carry out integrated coordination with the head of the district head to prevent overlapping work. Currently, between districts and regions, we have not found any clashes between the task forces. The government has provided an isolation place, namely the Islamic center, although it has not been inaugurated but it already has facilities with a record that it does not force patients (BPBD Indragiri Hilir, 2022).

V. CONCLUSION

The handling of the Covid-19 disaster in Riau Province is classified as very good. It can be seen from the Riau Government's preparedness indicators which prepare regulations and the implementation of disaster risk reduction for the spread of Covid-19 and the effectiveness of these regulations. It can be seen from the various efforts to establish regulations regarding Covid-19, namely Riau Governor Regulation number 55 of 2020 concerning the Implementation of Discipline and Law Enforcement of Health Protocols as an Effort to Prevent and Control Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) in Riau Province, Riau Governor Regulation no. Year 2020 concerning Amendments to the Fees of the Governor of Riau Regulation Number 40 of 2020 concerning Standard Costs for Special Treatments for Corona Virus Disease (COVID-19) in Riau Province and other regulations. From the regulations that have been set by the Riau Provincial Government through the

Pergub, the number of positive cases of Covid-19 has decreased. Even at the beginning of 2022, Riau Province was able to get 0 positive cases for a few days.

The Riau Provincial Government also continues to try to convey information related to Covid-19 on a regular basis. Even to do a door to door system to disseminate the information. One of the ways to do this is by issuing digital books on the Covid-19 response from the sub-district level and even to the RT/RW level. This is aimed at the obligation of every regional head at the sub-district, sub-district and even RT/RW levels to continue to disseminate information related to Covid-19 starting from knowledge about 5M and attitudes in dealing with the Covid-19 disaster. Every stakeholder also helps in handling Covid-19 such as several companies that carry out CSR in the form of distributing hand sanitizers, masks and other necessities. The Riau Regional Police also participated in the Covid-19 disaster management, namely by distributing vaccines in disadvantaged, frontier, outermost places so that the spread of vaccines ran smoothly. The Riau Police Chief is also a supervisor and enforcer of regulations related to violations committed by the community related to Covid-19.

REFERENCES

- [1]. BPBD Indragiri Hilir. (2022). *Kolaborasi Pentahelix dalam Penanggulangan Bencana Alan dan Covid-19 di Provinsi Riau Guna Mendukung Keamanan Nasional*. (Interview Result : 10 Maret 2022)
- [2]. Creswell, J. W. (1998). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five traditions*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- [3]. <https://corona.riau.go.id/> (access on Februari 19, 2022).
- [4]. <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/> (access on, April 1, 2022).
- [5]. Kabbidokes Polda Riau. (2022). *Kolaborasi Pentahelix dalam Penanggulangan Bencana Alan dan Covid-19 di Provinsi Riau Guna Mendukung Keamanan Nasional*. (Interview Result 10 Maret 2022)
- [6]. Kementerian Kesehatan Republik Indonesia. (2020). *Pedoman Kesiapsiagaan Menghadapi Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19)*. Jakarta : Direktorat Jendral Pencegahan dan Pengendalian Penyakit.
- [7]. Plt Kepala Dinas Kesehatan. (2022). *Kolaborasi Pentahelix dalam Penanggulangan Bencana Alan dan Covid-19 di Provinsi Riau Guna Mendukung Keamanan Nasional*. (Interview Result: 10 Maret 2022)
- [8]. Rahmawati., dkk. (2020). Edukasi Protokol Kesehatan dalam Menjalankan New Normal di Masa Pandemi Melalui Media Poster. Prosiding Seminar Nasional Pengabdian Masyarakat LPPM UMJ.
- [9]. Syafrizal, dkk. (2020). Pedoman Umum menghadapi Pandemi COVID-19 Bagi Pemerintah Daerah, Pencegahan, Pengendalian, Diagnosis dan Manajemen. (Access on April 1, 2022) https://www.kemendagri.go.id/documents/COVID-19/BUKU_PEDOMAN_COVID-19_KEMENDAGRI.pdf
- [10]. Triutomo, dkk. (2011). *Indeks rawan bencana Indonesia*. Jakarta : Badan Nasional Penanggulangan Bencana.
- [11]. Widyati, W., & Widana, I. D. K. K. (2021). Positive impacts of Covid-19 pandemic to strengthen National Health Defense. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 24(1), 562–570. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v24i1.4612>
- [12]. World Health Organization. (2020). Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). dari: https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/20200312-sitrep-52-covid-19.pdf?sfvrsn=e2bfc9c0_2 (Access on April 1, 2022)